

Acknowledgement

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Chemical Investigation of *Ougeinia dalbergioides*

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REINVESTIGATION of the heartwood of *Ougeinia dalbergioides* has yielded genistein, ferreirin, neophellamuretin, orobol and wedelolactone in addition to compounds already reported¹⁻³. This is the first report of the natural occurrence of neophellamuretin in free state and wedelolactone is a rare metabolite. The findings are placed below in Table 1.

TABLE 1—IDENTIFICATION OF COMPOUNDS IN
O. dalbergioides

Compound isolated	m.p. °C (Solvent of crystallisation)	Literature reference
Homoferreirin	166-67 (EtOAc/C ₆ H ₆)	1
Genistein	300 (EtOAc/C ₆ H ₆)	5
Ougenin	239-41 (EtOAc/C ₆ H ₆)	1
Ferreirin	210-11 (EtOAc/C ₆ H ₆)	5
Neophellamuretin	189-91 (EtOAc/petroleum ether)	3
Dalbergiodin	230-32 (EtOAc/C ₆ H ₆)	1
Orobol	270-72 (EtOAc)	5
Kaempferol	275-77 (MeOH/CHCl ₃)	2
Wedelolactone	327-30 (MeOH)	4

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The ¹H nmr spectrum (CDCl₃) of neophellamuretin acetate (Ac₂O/Py) displayed the following peaks (δ): 7.50 (d, 2H, J=8.5Hz, H-2', H-6'), 7.18 (d, 2H, J=8.5Hz, H-3', H-5'), 6.62 (s, 1H, H-6), 5.45, 5.75 (2d, 1H each, J=12.5Hz, H-2, H-3), 5.10 (br, 1H, CH of prenyl), 3.25 (d, 2H, J=7.5Hz, CH₂ of prenyl), 2.38 (s, 3H, phenolic acetoxy), 2.32 (s, 6H, two phenolic acetoxy), 2.02 (s, 3H, aliphatic acetoxy), 1.55, 1.68 (2s, 6H, gem methyls). The identity as neophellamuretin was confirmed by direct comparison with an authentic sample of neophellamuretin kindly gifted by Prof. M. Hasegawa who had isolated³ phellamurin (neophellamuretin glycoside) from *Phelladendron amurense* (Rutaceae).

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Solvent Extraction of Uranium(VI) with Versatic 911

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CONSIDERABLE interest has developed in recent years on the extraction of metals with high molecular weight carboxylic acids¹. In this communication, a rapid and selective method for the extraction of uranium(VI) with liquid cation exchanger, Versatic 911, in benzene is reported. Uranium(VI) has been quantitatively extracted at pH 5.5-6.0 from 0.1 M acetate solution with 1.81 M Versatic 911. The effect of variables such as pH, diluent, contact time, extractant concentration and acetate ion concentration has been investigated. The organic phase has been stripped with 2 M nitric acid. A probable composition of the extracted species, UO₂R₂.2RH (RH = Versatic 911), has been proposed. The presence of manganese(II), iron(III), cobalt(II), nickel(II), copper(II), zinc(II), cadmium(II), silver(I),

lanthanum(III), cerium(IV), praseodymium(III), mercury(II), thallium(I), lead(II), and thorium(IV) does not interfere in the extraction. Quantitative separation of uranium(VI) from several synthetic mixtures has been achieved.

Experimental

Elico pH meter, model LI-10, was used for the measurement of pH.

Versatic 911: (Shell Chemical, London), A liquid mixture of saturated tertiary monocarboxylic acids of C₉, C₁₀, and C₁₁ chain length, manufactured from C₉-C₁₁ olefines²⁻³. The concentration and purity of Versatic 911 was 5.43 M and 99.0%, respectively⁴. The sample was used as such.

Uranyl acetate solution (1.05 mg/ml): 2.1 g UO₂(NO₃)₂·6H₂O was dissolved in deionized water. Uranyl acetate solution was prepared from the nitrate solution by precipitation of uranyl hydroxide and subsequent dissolution in 1 litre 0.2 M acetic acid. The solution was standardised by complexometric titration following back titration procedure with standard thorium nitrate solution using xylenol orange indicator⁵.

Extraction procedures: The aqueous phase containing 10.5 mg uranium in 0.1 M acetic acid was equilibrated with 10 ml 1.81 M Versatic 911 in benzene for 5 min. The distribution coefficient reached a constant value within 5 min of shaking. The two layers were allowed to settle for 10 min. The aqueous phase was separated and the equilibrium pH measured. The aqueous phase was washed with 5 ml benzene to remove the traces of organic solvent entrained in it. The resulting benzene extract was mixed with the organic phase. The organic phase was stripped with 20 ml 2 M nitric acid for 5 min. The acid extract was carefully withdrawn and again washed with 5 ml benzene to remove the entrained solvent. The amount of uranium present in both aqueous and organic phase was estimated by complexometric titration. All the extraction experiments were performed at 25 ± 0.5°.

Results and Discussion

Diluents: Various diluents, viz., benzene, toluene, xylene, carbontetrachloride, chloroform, diisopropyl ether and nitrobenzene were tried for the extraction of uranium under the optimum condition. Quantitative extraction was achieved in most of the cases excepting the last two where emulsion formation took place. Benzene was used as diluent in all the extraction experiment.

Acidity: The extraction of uranium(VI) with Versatic 911 at various pH was performed at constant acetate concentration (0.1 M). With constant extractant (1.81 M) and metal concentration (2.2 × 10⁻³ M), extraction of uranium increased with increase in pH upto 6.0 and was quantitative in the pH range 5.5-6.0.

Ammonium sulphate: The effect of ammonium sulphate on extraction at different pH was studied by changing ammonium sulphate concentration from 0.5 to 3 M in the aqueous phase while the uranium concentration was maintained constant. At constant pH, the extraction decreased with increase in ammonium sulphate in the aqueous phase. This decrease may be due to the formation of less extractable species as has been suggested for Versatic 911 in other system²⁻³.

Acetate ion: The extraction of uranium(VI) decreases with increase in acetate ion concentration. This decrease may be due to the formation of less extractable acetate species in the aqueous phase. The experiments were carried out at constant metal (2.2 × 10⁻³ M) and extractant concentration (1.81 M). log D is proportional to log [acetate] and the slope of logarithmic curve is -2.1, indicating the release of two acetate ions in the extraction process.

Versatic 911: The effect of extractant concentration was studied by changing the concentration of Versatic 911 from 1.08 × 10⁻² to 1.81 M using benzene diluent. Neat (or undiluted) Versatic 911 forms emulsion with water and the tendency to do this increases with increasing pH. To minimize this tendency, all of the experiments were carried out using Versatic 911 in benzene at not greater than 1.81 M. In order to determine the probable composition of the extracted species log D was plotted against log [Versatic 911] which produced a straight line with slope 1.94. Shibata *et al*⁶ showed that Versatic 911 exists as dimer in non-polar solvents like benzene. So, the extraction mechanism of uranium can be proposed as:

R₂H₂ denotes the dimeric form of Versatic 911 in benzene solution. Release of two acetate is supported from the plot of log D against log [acetate], which gave a slope of 2.1.

Extractive separation: Uranium was separated from several binary mixtures using the recommended extraction condition. The procedure being very simple and rapid, required in most cases only the control of pH. Calcium, magnesium, strontium and barium did not interfere in the extraction. The interference of nickel, copper, silver and mercury was removed by masking with potassium cyanide. The interference of cobalt was removed by masking with ammonium thiocyanate. Potassium cyanide, ammonium thiocyanate and EDTA did not interfere. Molybdate, vanadate, tungstate, oxalate, citrate and tartrate interfered in the extraction. The interferences of manganese, iron(III), zinc, cadmium, lanthanum, cerium(IV), praseodymium, thallium(I), lead and thorium(IV) were removed by masking with EDTA. In these cases, excepting for iron, two consecutive extractions were required at the optimum condition, while for iron(III) three consecutive extractions at pH 4.5 were required. The effect of foreign ions and their tolerance limits are shown in Table 1. In order to assess the possible analytical

NOTES

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF FOREIGN IONS ON EXTRACTION
ON URANIUM(VI)

Foreign ion	Concentration $\times 10^{-3} M$	Uranium extracted %	Error %
Mg ⁺⁺	8	99.5	-0.5
Ca ⁺⁺	5	99.0	-1.0
Sr ⁺⁺	2	99.3	-0.7
Ba ⁺⁺	1.4	99.6	-0.4
Mn ⁺⁺	3.6	99.4	-0.6
Fe ⁺⁺	3.5	99.5	-0.5
Co ⁺⁺	3.4	100.4	+0.3
Ni ⁺⁺	3.4	99.5	-0.5
Cu ⁺⁺	3	98.6	-1.4
Zn ⁺⁺	3	99.6	-0.4
Ag ⁺	1.8	99.5	-0.5
Cd ⁺⁺	1.7	99.2	-0.8
La ⁺⁺	1.4	99.7	-0.3
Ce ⁺⁺	1.4	100.7	+0.6
Pr ⁺⁺	1.4	99.5	-0.5
Hg ⁺⁺	1	100.9	+0.8
Tl ⁺	9	99.5	-0.5
Pb ⁺⁺	9	99.0	-1.0
Th ⁺⁺	8	98.6	-1.4
SCN ⁻	3.4	99.0	-1.0
CN ⁻	8	99.8	-0.1
EDTA	5	99.6	-0.4

application, the proposed method was used for the extraction of uranium(VI) from several synthetic mixtures prepared by mixing 5 mg of each metal (excepting uranium of which 10 mg was taken) :

1. U(VI)+Ce(IV)+Th(IV) ;
2. U(VI)+La(III)+Ce(IV)+Th(IV) ;
3. U(VI)+Co(II)+Ni(II)+Hg(II) ;
4. U(VI)+Ca(II)+Sr(II)+Ba(II).

In the cases of (1) and (2) EDTA was used as masking agent whereas in (3) KCN was used. Two consecutive extractions were carried out in the cases of (1) and (2). In all the cases quantitative recovery of uranium(VI) was achieved.

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